

Supplementary material for

**What is your Prior Worth? Effective
Sample Size and Sample Size Planning for
Gaussian Graphical Models**

– AUTHOR INFORMATION REMOVED FOR BLINDED REVIEW –

S1 Supplementary Figures

S1.1 Simulation Study on Prior ESS: Descriptive Summaries

Figure S1: Distribution of partial correlations $\rho_{ij} = -K_{ij}/\sqrt{K_{ii}K_{jj}}$ for all off-diagonal pairs (i, j) of the simulated precision matrices. Violin plots with interquartile range are stratified by graph structure (rows) and prior study size ν (columns), with network size p on the horizontal axis. Each box summarizes $R = 1,000$ replications. Outliers are not displayed to improve the visualization. The dashed horizontal line marks $\rho_{ij} = 0$.

Figure S2: Distribution of marginal variances $\text{Var}(\mathbf{x}_i)$ of the simulated precision matrices. Violin plots with interquartile range are stratified by graph structure (rows) and prior study size ν (columns), with network size p on the horizontal axis. Each box summarizes $R = 1,000$ replications. Outliers are not displayed to improve the visualization.

Figure S3: Distribution of the log condition number $\log(\kappa(\mathbf{K}))$ of the simulated precision matrices. Violin plots with interquartile range are stratified by graph structure (rows) and prior study size ν (columns), with network size p on the horizontal axis. Each box summarizes $R = 1,000$ replications. Outliers are not displayed to improve the visualization.

S1.2 Simulation Study on Prior ESS: Density-dependent Behavior of ESS/ν (VR and PR)

Figure S4: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for random structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S5: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for small-world structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S6: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for scale-free structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S7: **Parameterwise ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S8: **Parameterwise ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for random structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S9: **Parameterwise ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for small-world structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S10: **Parameterwise ESS/ν ratio as a function of network density, for scale-free structures.** Each curve shows the median ratio ESS/ν across network density, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

S1.3 Simulation Study on Prior ESS: Drivers

Figure S11: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of the normalized clustering coefficient.** Each curve shows the centroid ESS/ν against the clustering coefficient, normalized to $[0, 1]$ within each (p, ν) configuration, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S12: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of the log condition number of the numerator matrix for the corresponding ESS estimator ($\log \kappa_{\text{num}}$).** Each curve shows the centroid ESS/ν against the log condition number, normalized to $[0, 1]$ within each (p, ν) configuration, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

Figure S13: **Global ESS/ν ratio as a function of the average strength metric.** Each curve shows the centroid ESS/ν against the average strength, normalized to $[0, 1]$ within each (p, ν) configuration, where ν is the prior study size. Columns index the network size p , rows separate the two estimators, ESS_{VR}/ν (top) and ESS_{PR}/ν (bottom). Line color encodes $\nu \in \{25, 50, 100, 200\}$. The dotted line marks $ESS/\nu = 1$, where the prior ESS and ν are equal.

S1.4 Simulation Study on Sample Size Planning

Figure S14: \log_{10} planned sample size relative to ESS_{VR} across prior study size ν . Each panel shows $\log_{10}(n^*/ESS_{VR})$ as a function of ν , where n^* is a planned sample size and the denominator ESS_{VR} is fixed. Columns index the network size p , rows differ in how n^* is determined: the BFDA planned sample sizes under each hypothesis, \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 (top two rows), and the global and parameterwise DPIP recommended sample sizes, $DPIP_{global}$ and $DPIP_{pw}$ (bottom two rows). Line color and line type distinguish dense (black, solid) from sparse (gray, dash-dotted) networks. The \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 rows use a Bayes factor threshold = 3.0. The dotted horizontal line marks 0, where the planned sample size equals ESS_{VR} .

S2 Supplementary Tables

S2.1 Bayesian Power at DPIR Planned Size

		$p = 10$				$p = 20$				$p = 30$			
ν		25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200
Dense	\mathcal{H}_0	0.33	0.47	0.56	0.77	0.43	0.40	0.55	0.66	–	0.35	0.43	0.61
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.39	0.48	0.55	0.76	0.52	0.41	0.55	0.66	–	0.35	0.46	0.61
Sparse	\mathcal{H}_0	0.21	0.24	0.45	0.67	0.47	0.37	0.33	0.41	–	0.45	0.41	0.40
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.41	0.42	0.51	0.64	0.58	0.48	0.44	0.50	–	0.53	0.47	0.50

Table S1: Median BFDA power for \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 evaluated at the global DPIR recommended sample size n^* , across prior study sizes ν (columns, nested within p). Bayes factor threshold = 3.

		$p = 10$				$p = 20$				$p = 30$			
ν		25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200
Dense	\mathcal{H}_0	0.45	0.56	0.62	0.80	0.57	0.54	0.64	0.72	–	0.53	0.55	0.68
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.49	0.55	0.60	0.79	0.60	0.53	0.63	0.70	–	0.51	0.54	0.67
Sparse	\mathcal{H}_0	0.30	0.32	0.52	0.71	0.48	0.41	0.36	0.45	–	0.46	0.43	0.42
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.47	0.47	0.54	0.68	0.61	0.52	0.48	0.54	–	0.56	0.51	0.54

Table S2: Median BFDA power for \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 evaluated at the pairwise DPIR recommended sample size n^* , across prior study sizes ν (columns, nested within p). Bayes factor threshold = 3.

		$p = 10$				$p = 20$				$p = 30$			
ν		25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200	25	50	100	200
Dense	\mathcal{H}_0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.32	–	0.00	0.00	0.26
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.35	0.40	0.47	0.69	0.43	0.37	0.48	0.55	–	0.36	0.39	0.54
Sparse	\mathcal{H}_0	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.40	0.23	0.10	0.08	–	0.40	0.29	0.23
	\mathcal{H}_1	0.34	0.34	0.39	0.55	0.57	0.41	0.35	0.39	–	0.51	0.43	0.41

Table S3: Median BFDA power for \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 evaluated at the pairwise DPIR recommended sample size n^* , across prior study sizes ν (columns, nested within p). Bayes factor threshold = 10.